

Tobi, your I2I ambassador

PREVENTION AND RESPONSE TO SEXUAL VIOLENCE CHECKLIST

May 2024

BACKGROUND

- Women and girls' experience of sexual violence (SV) is prevalent across geographies. Women who experience physical or sexual intimate partner violence are significantly more likely to acquire HIV. Persons who have recently acquired HIV experience higher rates of SV.
- A **rapid review** gathered and synthesised research from 41 peer-reviewed recent articles that quantitatively measured the effectiveness of interventions to prevent or respond to SV from all 15 South to South Learning Network (SSLN) countries to better understand what types of SV interventions are being implemented, if they are effective, and to provide insights to strengthen SV programming.

PURPOSE

Building on the evidence synthesised during the review, this checklist is designed to help stakeholders quickly assess potential areas of focus for their SV programming.

In my country context	Assessment (check appropriate box)			Reason for sub-optimal performance (if applicable)	Next steps: Prioritise which elements need to be addressed, and state short- and longer-term plans to address them
	Absent	Present but not optimal	Present and working well		
Policy, strategy, and guidelines					
National HIV prevention strategy includes a focus on SV prevention	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Gender-based violence/ violence against women legislation is in place and enforced	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Program design and implementation					
SV prevention programs implemented as part of HIV prevention programs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
SV prevention programs engage girls and boys during adolescence (e.g. through school-based programs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Services to provide an immediate response after SV/assault integrated as part of ANC, HIV, SRH services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
HIV prevention services (HIV testing, PEP, PrEP) offered as part of SV services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Health care providers (including frontline workers) trained to deliver SV prevention and response programs and services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Rehabilitation or long-term psychosocial support for SV survivors provided	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Community leaders engaged to address norms around violence against women	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Operational Integration					
A TWG and/or advisory committee has been established and is actively engaged in discussions on SV prevention policies and programs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Evidence					
Data on the scale of SV experience among women and girls	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Evidence on SV prevention and response for marginalised populations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Funding and resource allocation					
Funding allocated to SV prevention response within HIV programming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Funding allocated to SV programming within other ministries	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

For support with using the PREVENTION AND RESPONSE TO SEXUAL VIOLENCE CHECKLIST, please contact your country engagement lead.

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